

A Review on the Ductile Beam Column Connection for Precast Concrete Structures

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Abstract The beam-column connections form an integral part of any building, the failure of which can endanger the stability of the entire structure. Recent trends in construction have witnessed a growing interest in precast construction owing to its reduced construction time, concrete wastage, ease of assembly and preventing concrete failure at the construction site during erection. However, contrary to conventional RC structures, the beam-column connections in precast concrete structures are not standardized and it is often difficult to achieve continuity between the members. Although several International design standards exist for precast concrete structures, the current available Indian building codes do not include capacious design and analysis specifications for the precast concrete beam-column connection systems. This limits the applicability of precast structures in high seismic zones where the beam-column connections play a pivotal role. The precast connection should satisfy the strong column and weak beam mechanisms for satisfactory seismic performance. Several researchers have developed suitable configurations for the precast beam-column connections to ensure adequate seismic performance. Numerous experimental and numerical investigations have been carried out by these researchers to propose an economical and practical solution for the ductile precast concrete connections. This paper presents a systematic review of the design standards for precast concrete and the research carried out till date in developing solutions for the ductile connection problem in precast concrete structures. The major topics that this review addressed are given below: (1) Current Indian and International Standards for precast concrete connections. (2) The various types and configurations of precast beam-column joints. (3) Experimental and numerical studies on the seismic performance of precast beam-column connections. (4) Studies on innovative hybrid beam-column connections. The failure patterns, energy dissipation, lateral strength, stiffness, and displacement ductility were some of the parameters considered for the evaluation of the seismic performance of the precast connections.

Keywords Precast concrete structures, Beam-Column connections, Seismic performance, Hybrid precast connections.

Introduction

Precast is a type of construction method in which the building components or elements are assembled off-site in a controlled environment before being transported to the construction site for assembly. Concrete is the most common material which is used to produce these precast components, but other materials like steel and composite materials can also be employed. Structural components such as walls, columns, beams, slabs, and other structural and architectural components can be made precast. This method is often employed in construction projects that involve residential buildings, commercial structures, bridges, and other infrastructure. Precast construction has many advantages including enhanced quality control, accelerated construction schedules, cost savings, durability, architectural flexibility, reduced site disturbance, environmental friendliness, and the ability to produce dependable and long-lasting building components compared to reinforced concrete structures. Although precast construction offers several benefits over conventional RC construction, their seismic performance needs to be assessed particularly in seismic prone regions of our country. A research team led by Dr. Ajay Chourasia of Central Building Research Institute (CBRI) Roorkee is currently developing full scale models of precast concrete structures to test their seismic performance. The precast construction however also includes certain drawbacks such as the initial outlay of funds, transportation expenses, restricted on-site time, adjustments, design limitations, weather dependence, connection problems, difficulties obtaining permits and equipment maintenance. For precast concrete structures to be secure and safe for use, beam-column connections are required. They provide the durability and compatibility of the structure under varied loads by transferring forces and moments between the precast elements. In earthquake design, stronger column-weak beam mechanisms which offer superior stability, energy dissipation, and ductility than strong beam-weak column mechanisms are recommended for reinforced concrete frame structures. The generation of plastic hinges at the beam ends rather than the column ends is ensured by strong column-weak beam processes, which can stop the structure from collapsing altogether. Because the beams can be lighter and smaller than the columns, strong column-weak beam mechanisms also enable more economical use of materials. The critical elements in a precast concrete structure are the beam-column connections which might lead to a progressive collapse if improper bond exists between the different precast elements. In precast structures, various connection types are employed based on the project requirements and the nature of the precast elements. In Jointed Connections, the dowels are inserted during casting, ensuring alignment on-site for structural continuity. Grout Connections (Choi, *et al.* 2013) involve pouring cement grout into joints after placing prefabricated parts, enhancing stability and load transfer. Precast elements also utilize Threaded rods or steel bolts (Ye *et al.* 2021) for connection. Bolt holes are typically cast during production, enabling quick on-site assembly, and this connection is referred to as Bolted Connections (Gao *et al.* 2019). Headed studs, (Ghayeb *et al.* 2017) like shear connectors, are commonly employed to transfer loads when connecting precast concrete beams to columns or other supports. In precast construction, welding is used for joining steel components and creating a durable connection (Wu *et al.* 2020). Precast elements are bonded with special adhesives or epoxies for a clean, attractive appearance, particularly in applications aiming to conceal mechanical connectors. Corbels (Fan *et al.* 2020) in precast construction support beams or slabs and may include openings for pockets or recesses, especially in connections like precast columns to foundations. Slip-critical connections limit movement for seismic resistance, while

Panel-to-Panel Connections use inserts, anchors, or fasteners in precast concrete wall systems. Depending on the type of joint, connections can be either dry or wet. Beam-to-column connections include grouted sleeves, embedded plates, bolted flanges, and welded flanges, used to unite beams at an angle in structures like trusses or portal frames. Similarly, beam-to-beam couplings, such as haunches, cleats, and gusset plates, depend on the type of joint, which can be either dry or wet connections. Various codes and standards are applied in precast construction to ensure the quality, safety, and performance of elements. The Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) oversees building standards in India, and frequently applied codes include IS456-2000, a comprehensive guide for precast and RCC, covering every aspect of design and construction with criteria for materials, structural design, and production methods applicable to precast elements.

Design Standards for Precast Concrete

Several International standards have laid down recommendations for the design of precast concrete elements. Most of the available standards are for structural reinforced concrete design with provisions for precast concrete while the standards exclusively for precast concrete are limited. Guidelines and specifications for seismic design are provided by the Chinese code GB/T 50011-2010 to improve a building's resistance to earthquakes, guaranteeing safety and preventing casualties. The code supplies guidelines for professionals in China to design earthquake-resistant buildings by outlining principles, criteria, and procedures. GB/T 50081-2016 related to precast construction, offers guidelines, requirements, and standards for conducting precast construction in China. GB/T 50448-2015 also related to precast construction, offers guidelines, standards, and specifications for designing, producing, transporting, and assembling precast elements in Chinese construction projects. It ensures precast elements meet structural and safety requirements, covering design, manufacturing, transportation, and assembly, while showing measures for quality control throughout the entire process from production to installation. The American codes that deal with precast concrete are ACI 374.1-05 which shows rules and recommendations for the planning, production, transportation, and assembling of precast concrete components. Establishing industry best practices, safety precautions, and quality standards for the duration of the precast concrete process is its primary goal. To assure the safety, structural integrity, and quality of precast elements in construction projects, ACI 374.1-05 addresses design standards, manufacturing procedures, transportation considerations, assembly guidelines, and quality control measures. ACI 352R-02 guidance on beam-column interaction in monolithic constructions to precast connections recognizes the distinct behaviour of precast elements. Extract detailing requirements from ACI 352R-02, particularly for joint detailing and reinforcement, adjusting as needed for precast connections to ensure right details for longevity and structural soundness. The code of practice for structural concrete design in Singapore is the CP 65: Part 1-1999. This specification is common for precast and reinforced concrete structures. It analyses load concerns, considers material qualities, covers a range of structural aspects, and provides a logical design process with safety factors. To guarantee conformity with the most recent requirements, the code places an important priority on quality control throughout construction and suggests still being up to current on changes. From the Indian context several codes are available which deal with the design of precast elements. The code IS 456-2000 outlines criteria for the structural design of concrete elements, encompassing precast components, to ensure that connections meet necessary strength and stability requirements. IS 15916-2020 is used for building design and erection using prefabricated concrete code of practice addresses the design and construction of buildings made from precast concrete. IS 3935-1966 related to composite construction, seeks guidelines for integrating various construction materials, including precast concrete. IS10297-1982 gives the specifications on planning and constructing floors and roofs with precast ribbed or cored slab units. The seismic design factors that apply to precast connections are taken following IS 3920-2016 code, these codes offer some design details for precast construction, but they do not provide a complete set of guidelines. As a result, it is necessary to consult international codes for the design of precast connections. Although several International codes for reinforced concrete have provisions for precast concrete, the lack of an exclusive design standard for precast concrete design makes it difficult for designers to work with precast structures particularly with regards to the beam-column connections in high rise buildings and in seismic zones. This has led several researchers to explore reliable and ductile connection configurations which would be discussed in the succeeding section.

Literature Survey

In precast concrete constructions, wet precast connections involve bonding precast pieces by adding reinforcement bars or accessories to the concrete at the joints. Unlike dry precast connections, which rely on welding or bolting between embedded arrangements in precast pieces, wet precast connections involve cast-in-situ concreting to achieve the bond between the connected precast members. Some key benefits of wet type connections include higher structural integrity and continuity compared to dry precast connections, accommodating greater tolerances and irregularities in precast elements, and offering stronger defense against seismic forces and progressive collapse. Dry connections on the other hand offer greater resilience and repairability compared to emulative cast-in-situ technologies, allowing for quicker and easier assembly. They show reduced shrinkage and creep. Examples of dry connections include end plates, stiffener plates and bolts, UPT tendons, and replaceable energy dissipation connectors. Several types of dry precast connections exist, depending on connection details and structural behavior. In these connections, steel plates are embedded at the extremities of precast elements and then fastened together on-site. These connections employ unique components that can be easily swapped out following an earthquake and can absorb seismic energy. One of the most crucial elements in the design of precast concrete structures is the design of beam-column connections. Depending on the purpose and loads, several types of ordinary reinforced concrete and hybrid connections are used. The typical method for creating wet concrete connections

is to pour concrete into the space created by the prefabricated elements. In dry connection, the precast elements are joined together with bolts or welds and steel plates. In hybrid connections, structural steel sections either embedded in concrete or exposed are used in conjunction with the precast concrete elements. Hybrid connections can either be wet or dry. With regards to strength, energy dissipation, and lateral ductility, hybrid connections are just as capable as monolithic RC connections, offering stronger resistance to seismic forces and progressive collapse when compared to ordinary precast connections. Several researchers have proposed various configurations of wet, dry and hybrid precast beam-column connections each offering its own set of merits and demerits. The following section discusses some of the most recent research on the seismic performance of various types of precast connections.

Wet Connections

In comparing the results of Lin, *et al.* (2021) and Deng, *et al.* (2020), Lin, *et al.* (2021) focused on the use of an ultrahigh-performance concrete (UHPC) shell with specific design features, resulting in a specimen that showed 1.32% higher ductility, dissipated energy, and stiffness compared to RC specimens. They also noted small flexural cracks and no concrete spalling in the connection zone, with the precast specimen having 80mm ultrahigh-performance concrete shell thickness, showing the best result from their survey. On the other hand, Deng, *et al.* (2020) examined the use of bottom longitudinal reinforcement supplied by the beam and upper longitudinal reinforcement running through the entire beam-column connection, with the longitudinal bars piercing the steel sleeve during column assembly. Their specimen, meant to demonstrate the potential of highly ductile Fiber reinforcement (HDC) replacing concrete in the joint, showed a marginal increase in displacement by 1.62% and minimal fractures without concrete spalling. Based on these findings, Lin, *et al.* (2021) UHPC shell design appears to offer better overall performance in terms of ductility, energy dissipation, and stiffness compared to Deng, *et al.* (2020) approach. It is clear from comparing the findings of Zhang, *et al.* (2020) and Beni and Madhkhan (2022) that both investigations concentrated on using specific design elements to enhance the performance of beam-column connections. With a ratio of 0.75% of tensile rebar in beams, (Beni and Madhkhan 2022) monolithic specimen demonstrated exceptional load-carrying performance and increased energy dissipation in the connection zone in the positive loading direction. With the employment of two stiffener plates, T-bearing plates, and a T-section steel plate positioned horizontally at the end of the precast beam-column, it was also discovered that the ductility of the monolithic specimen was 0.98% higher than that of the precast specimen. Zhang, *et al.* (2020) in contrast, concentrated on the application of SFC, vertical and horizontal I-shaped steel beams, and flange cover plates in the connection zone. Their specimens showed diagonal cracks in the joint and flexural cracks in the beam at the joint area. In general, they were more ductile and dissipated higher energies than the RC specimen. The favourable results of their study were ascribed to the existence of SFC in addition to vertical and horizontal steel beams. All things considered, both studies show how certain design elements can enhance the performance of beam-column connections. In comparison to RC specimens, hybrid connections with a flexural strength ratio of 1.55 showed highest displacement (49%) and maximum ductility (1.24%), as well as strength degradation, according to the authors Ghayeb, *et al.* (2020). When compared to RCC in the push loading direction, the main steel plate and one gusset plate found in the beam-column connection region showed 1.27% higher initial stiffness and higher energy dissipation, indicating the appropriateness for seismic zones. The authors concentrated on hybrid connections that were seismically suitable and had high flexural strength. However, specimens with several tendons going through the beam-to-column connections, a connection that doesn't connect the slabs were provided by Kim, *et al.* (2021). There were no cracks in the slab. Having maximum joint shear and ductility that are 2.42% higher. A comparison of the two studies, with Kim, *et al.* (2021) showing a 2.42% improvement in ductility. In a study by Li, *et al.* (2023) a specimen equipped with 16mm thickness of end plates of the end beam near the column demonstrated a satisfactory performance, exhibiting minimal failure, lower cracks, and a maximum yield displacement of 1.58%. This specimen also displayed 1.4% higher ductility and 1.11% greater energy dissipation. However, the remaining hybrid connections, including the cast-in-situ specimen's concrete, were crushed, indicating the higher ultimate load-carrying capacity of the cast-in-situ specimen. On the other hand, Xue, *et al.* (2021) investigated specimens with longitudinal rebars joined by welding and complete grouting sleeves in the beam and column, respectively. The precast exterior joint specimen achieved a ductility 1.09% higher than the reinforced concrete connection, while the precast interior joint specimen had a ductility 0.98% lower than the reinforced concrete connection. Additionally, the interior precast specimen exhibited higher displacement and energy dissipation, while the exterior precast specimen displayed more flexural cracks. These findings collectively highlight the diverse performance characteristics of different hybrid connections, emphasizing factors such as ductility, energy dissipation, and crack patterns Li, *et al.* (2023); Xue, *et al.* (2021). According to Feng, *et al.* (2021) their specimen had a maximum displacement of 1.06% and a total dissipated energy of 1.3% more than other specimens. Large stiffness, a high drift ratio and greater ductility were the outcomes of the assembly with average initial pre tensioning force of single steel strand. However, when compared to RC specimens, the specimen beam-to-column connection filled with steel fibre concrete (SFC) in Zhang, *et al.* (2020) investigation showed 1.34% larger displacement, 3.307% higher energy dissipation, and reduced strength deterioration. A comparison of those results revealed no concrete spalling, diagonal fractures in joints, and flexural cracks in beams close to the joint region, greater ductility in the specimens. Choi, *et al.* (2013) found that precast exterior connection specimens filled with wet concrete developed for the Engineering cementitious composite exhibited more ductility and energy dissipation than specimens cast in place, with minimal concrete spalling and fewer diagonal cracks in the joint zone, despite observing flexural cracks at the beam end. In contrast, Choi, *et al.* (2013) & Choi, *et al.* (2020) focused on precast interior specimens filled with wet concrete specifically developed for the ECC, which showed a peak load comparable to the cast-in-place

specimen, with higher ductility and joint shear. The study by Fan, et al. (2020) appears to demonstrate better seismic performance in terms of ductility, energy dissipation, stiffness, and load-carrying capacity compared to the findings of Gao, et al. (2019). Fan, et al. (2020) reported higher ductility, greater stiffness, and enhanced energy dissipation in the precast interior connection, indicating superior seismic behaviour. Additionally, the increased flexural rebar area in the beam contributed to higher dissipated energy. In contrast, Gao, et al. (2019) emphasized the benefits of shear studs, steel beams, and bolted connections but did not provide specific performance improvements comparable to the results presented by Fan, et al. (2020). Therefore, the study by Fan et al. (2020) appears to offer better results in terms of seismic performance for precast interior beam-column connections. Zhang, et al. (2023) utilized hooked and headed bars in the connection zone, while Singhal, et al. (2021) used longitudinal bars and lateral ties with specific anchorage and development lengths the maximum load capacity for the precast exterior connection, while Singhal, et al. (2021) evaluated the maximum displacement, stiffness, and ductility of the connection and reported better results for these parameters. Wahjudi, et al. (2014) observed similar stiffness values for the interior connection with U-bent bar anchorage compared to other specimens, while Guan, et al. (2019) reported higher ductility, energy dissipation capacity, and similar drift ratio for the precast interior connection with high-strength steel rebars. Therefore, both studies offer valuable insights into the design and performance of precast interior beam-column connections, and further research is needed to determine the most effective design strategies for achieving optimal seismic behaviour and structural integrity. The study by Chen, et al. (2022) demonstrates that the hybrid prefabricated concrete (HPC) exterior connections exhibit higher levels of ductility (1.17%) and displacement (1.46%) compared to precast specimens. However, concrete spalling has been observed in the HPC specimen. On the other hand, Guerrero, et al. (2019) found that the post-tensioned beam-column generally has more ductility and energy dissipation compared to other specimens. However, minor cracks and brittle failures were observed in the precast specimen with a bracket that had a 150mm beam stirrup spacing. Chen, et al. (2022) demonstrated that the HPC exterior connections exhibit higher levels of ductility and displacement compared to precast specimens, with good hysteresis curves. However, concrete spalling was observed in the HPC specimen. Guerrero, et al. (2019) reported that the post-tensioned beam-column generally has more ductility and energy dissipation compared to other specimens. However, minor cracks and brittle failures were observed in the precast specimen with a bracket that had a 150mm beam stirrup spacing. The study by Xue, et al. (2022) indicates that the precast connections exhibit higher ductility, but lower bearing capacity compared to the cast-in-place specimens. On the other hand, the study by Feng, et al. (2018) discusses the reinforcement diameters of the beam-column connectors, as well as the impact of stirrup spacing on the peak strength of the connections. In reviewing the performance of these two authors' studies, it is important to consider the specific objectives and parameters evaluated in each study. Xue, et al. (2022) focused on the comparison of interior and exterior connections, highlighting the differences in ductility, and bearing capacity between the precast and cast-in-place specimens. Their findings suggest that the precast connections exhibit higher ductility, but lower bearing capacity compared to the cast-in-place specimens. This indicates a trade-off between ductility and bearing capacity when using precast connections, which could be a crucial factor in seismic design and performance. On the other hand, Feng, et al. (2018) delved into the reinforcement diameters, and stirrup spacing of the beam-column connectors, providing insights into the impact of these parameters on the performance of the connections. In conclusion, both studies offer valuable insights into the performance of precast concrete beam-column connections, with Xue, et al. (2022) emphasizing the trade-off between ductility and bearing capacity, and Feng, et al. (2018) providing detailed analysis of specific design parameters and their effects on connection performance. The hybrid precast beam-column connection is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Hybrid precast beam-column connection

Dry Connections

The study by Huang, et al. (2022) demonstrated that specimens incorporating multi-slit devices (MSDs) with distinct shapes and high-strength fasteners exhibited superior performance in initial stiffness, energy dissipation, and ductility. The rectangular MSD showed 20% greater initial stiffness and energy dissipation, while the hexagonal MSD displayed

1.24% more ductility than monolithic connections (MC). Chen, et al. (2023) investigated precast concrete frame joints with a built-in disc spring mechanism, highlighting enhanced seismic performance. The interior precast specimen with a disc spring and grout sleeve at a 0.2 compression ratio displayed 1.14% higher ductility and higher initial stiffness compared to reinforced concrete (RC) specimens. The exterior specimen with a 0.4 compression ratio exhibited 1.06% higher ductility. Both connections demonstrated good hysteresis characteristics, with the interior precast specimen showing 1.22% higher displacement and shear deformation compared to RC connections. These studies collectively showcase the effectiveness of innovative components in improving the seismic performance of precast concrete connections, with each approach offering unique advantages in terms of stiffness, energy dissipation, and ductility. In comparing the results of Wu, et al. (2020) and Zhang, et al. (2022), it is evident that Wu, et al. (2020) found that bolted connections exhibited superior performance compared to welded and bolted-welded connections, with an ultimate displacement and maximum ductility that were significantly higher. They also noted that the bolted connection enhanced the mechanical performance of the joints and did not experience local crushing or buckling failure. On the other hand, Zhang, et al. (2022) focused on the use of a corbel at the end of the precast beam and a steel top connector, which resulted in a peak performance that was slightly higher than the monolithic specimen, albeit with slightly lower ductility and stiffness. Based on these findings, Wu, et al. (2020) bolted connections appear to offer better overall performance in terms of displacement, ductility, and mechanical enhancement compared to Zhang, et al. (2022) approach. It is evident from comparing the findings of Ye, et al. (2021) and Baran, et al. (2021) that the performance of beam-column connections under various loading scenarios was the primary goal of both investigations. In contrast to hybrid beam-column, Ye, et al. (2021) achieved more displacement and ductility by supporting the connections with I-sectional steel connectors, bolts, and cladding plates. Furthermore, they discovered that the CIS functioned well, having a 224.3 kN bearing capability. However, compared to monolithic specimens, Baran, et al. (2021) unique precast connecting approach produced better ductility. Also, they noticed that compared to other specimens, the beam with connecting plates had a larger drift ratio and energy dissipation. Overall, both studies provide valuable insights into the design and performance of beam-column connections in precast concrete structures. Comparing the performance of the column-to-column connections studied by Kulkarni, et al. (2008) and Ghayeb, et al. (2017) notable differences and similarities emerge. Kulkarni, et al. (2008) focused on an interior connection with a ductility factor of approximately 3.6, utilizing splice plates and bolts for the flanges and web beam end near the column. The study reported a larger initial displacement and observed pinching at a ductility factor of about 3.2. Finite Element Method (FEM) analysis was employed to assess the components of the connection. On the other hand, Ghayeb, et al. (2017) examined a connection with stiffener bonded to the steel plate, steel tube, and gusset plate, resulting in a maximum drift ratio of 9.5% and enhanced load carrying capacity. This cast-in specimen exhibited greater ductility in both loading directions, with similar fractures observed in both precast and cast-in-place specimens.

Discussions

High performance in comparison with monolithic RC connections was achieved by four research teams among those discussed in this report. These researchers have worked on innovative hybrid precast connections and compared the parameters of stiffness, displacement, dissipated energy, ductility, and failure modes of the proposed and conventional RC specimens. The study by Lin, et al. (2021) found that the precast specimen with ultrahigh-performance concrete had 80mm UHPC shell thickness and a grout sleeve at the bottom of the column demonstrated 1.32% higher ductility, dissipated energy, and stiffness compared to RC specimens. The connection, designed with a 0.71% stirrup ratio in the joint core and a 20mm grouted layer, featured thread-sleeve-headed rebars at the beam's bottom end with a compressive strength of 123.6 MPa and a tensile strength of 6.96 MPa. Among all tested specimens, the precast PU80 exhibited the best results, showing minimal flexural cracks and no concrete spalling in the connection zone. In the study by Huang, et al. (2022), specimens had higher performance in certain aspects compared to the specimens presented by other authors. The rectangular multi-silt devices were connected to the end of the beam near the column end. The results showed that the rectangular multi-silt device demonstrated a strong skeleton curve and greater load displacement, with 20% higher initial stiffness and energy dissipation compared to the hexagonal multi-silt device specimens. However, the hexagonal multi-silt device exhibited 1.24% greater ductility than the rectangular multi-silt device, with smaller fracture patterns visible. Therefore, the study concluded that the hexagonal multi-silt device showed better ductility compared to the rectangular multi-silt device. The study by Chen, et al. (2023) on precast specimens with the disc spring and grout sleeve with a 0.2 compression ratio given at the end of the beam close to the connection has better ductility, with 1.14% higher ductility compared to the studies by Kulkarni, et al. (2008), Ghayeb, et al. (2017), and Huang, et al. (2022). The connection has a 1.22% higher displacement. The main reason for that was that they used a disc spring and grout sleeves. Disc springs will give proper load distribution, superior flexibility to the entire structure, and absorb unexpected improper vibrations. Grout sleeves improve the strength of the specimen. This indicates better seismic performance in terms of deformation capacity and resistance to seismic forces. The study by Gao, et al. (2019) found that the addition of a slab without a tied connection increased the ductility of the common specification by 3.60%. Furthermore, the strength and ductility of the specified specimen were consistently enhanced by the bolted connection, resulting in smaller cracks. The slab, not connected by an

internal monolithic bolted connection, achieved a greater load displacement than the precast indications. From this study, the bolted connection gives better ductility, displacement, and stiffness. The bolt connections take longer to become brittle, and the stand has a higher load. The configurations adopted by the four research teams discussed above is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Different types of hybrid precast beam-column connection

Conclusions

Precast construction requires reduced labour, materials, construction time and offers higher strength and superior quality as compared to conventional RC structures. Compared to cast-in-situ construction, precast has a considerably lower impact on the environment since it generates less waste both on the construction site and in the factory. The most critical element of a precast concrete building is the beam-column connection which if fails can cause a catastrophic progressive collapse of the entire structure. The lack of relevant design standards has led several researchers to develop various configurations of resilient connections. The performance of a conventional precast connection is comparable to that of an average RC building and tends to be heavier and more difficult to shift and maintain. The use of hybrid connections tends to reduce the member sizes while also enhancing the strength, ductility and replaceability of the components. Components commonly adopted for hybrid connections are end plates, grout sleeves, disc springs and high-strength bolts. Research also shows that the addition of slabs has helped in improving the ductility of the hybrid beam-column connections. Most of the specimens reviewed in this survey were designed based on China, Japan, American, Europe and British standards, However, our country does not have a proper guideline or design methodology for the design of precast hybrid connections. Moreover, the international standards referred to in this report also do not provide guidelines for the design of hybrid connections. This constitutes the biggest gap in the current research on hybrid precast connections and warrants further exploration.

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